

Computational-Reumathological Cad Clinical Diagnosis with Lumbar Vertebral Cadaveric Specimens and Spine Sub-Units Mathematical Modeling. Part III

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ABSTRACT

Continuing this biomechanical research line, and based on previous series, a subsequent reumathologically-directed clinical study with 3D-CAD imaging-processing was done. In this part with GNU Octave and Matlab programming—comparing both. The lumbar cadaveric specimen is a different one related to previous publications specimens of bioengineering laboratory. The objective of the research is the clinical finding of lumbar spine degeneration signs, arthrosis, osteoarthritis, deformations, and disk herniations. The software method is presented in series of 3D-CAD lumbar vertebral imaging processing and software-camera with Matlab. Results demonstrate that, from scanned cloud data of cadaveric specimens, a clinical necropsia and diagnosis database can be taken out. Clinical applications on computational-forensics, computational-imaging intelligence, medical physics, and biomedical engineering are obtained from these cadaveric specimens 3D imaging-processing evaluation. A number of epidemiological/statistical data is shown. What is more, the author’s mathematical spine sub-unit model biomechanical equations and model is initially developed. The article is an advance and shows review of necessary parts for better understanding.

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KEYWORDS: computational anatomical dissection, image processing, software engineering, surfactal programming, computer aided design (CAD), computer aided manufacturing (CAM), anatomical cadaveric imaging simulations, biomechanics, bioengineering, spinal computational-surgery, spinal ligaments, spinal anterior longitudinal ligament (ALL), low back pain (LBP)

I. INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this subsequent part are to acquire the 3D Imaging process for diagnosis and comparative software results between GNU octave and Matlab images. Second one is the Lagrange outline of the Sub-Units vertebral model [16, Casesnoves-Bioengineering-Laboratory-Specimen-Model-4]. Enhancements of the study are up-to-date lumbar spine reumathology, pathology and biomechanical database for diagnosis, computational intelligence signs of degeneration, and mainly arthrosis clinical findings by using CAD analysis of scanned lumbar cadaveric specimens.

In this continuing study GNU-Octave, Illustrative Example 1, 3D imaging processing camera-pictures are

refined and shown. Illustrative Example 1 details how the lumbar vertebra surface can be examined with CAD.

Illustrative Example 1.- From former publications, a GNU-Octave with surface levels projections is shown. 3D Image-processing quality is acceptable. L3, L4, and L5 anterior facets from medial-left side can be studied. Vertebral bodies, disks, plates, and osteoarthritis signs. After that, it will be necessary to rotate the specimen searching the best vision angles and projections. The size of the image can be changed proportionally. [Casesnoves Bioengineering Laboratory Software 19.23].

Table 1.- Incidence and Prevalence of Lumbar Osteoarthritis and specially arthrosis lesions [24-36] with complementary explanations. Remark: all database from other authors is set as references numbers. The studies in several countries differ slightly, but the incidence is constantly high at everywhere.

SPECIAL SURGICAL-REUMATHOLOGICAL AND NEUROSURGEY LUMBAR SPINE CHARACTERISTICS	
CAUSE	CONSEQUENCE
The biomechanical load, despite the hard and resistant structure of vertebral bodies given by their natural optimal design, is so significant/constant	(LBP) is estimated to range from 15% to 20% in the US and from 25% to 45% in Europe [4-20].
When any patient lifts a weight, the reaction forces of the disk could reach around 6.000 N [3].	For this and other causes, such as biomechanical continuous movements dealing with high loads, trunk rotations, disk nutrition defaults, and recent increased times of postural and sedentarism at workplace, the spinal column degenerates far earlier than other musculoskeletal tissues [4-19].
Trunk rotations, disk nutrition defaults, and recent increased times of postural and sedentarism at workplace.	the spinal column degenerates far earlier than other musculoskeletal tissues [4-19].
Humans evolution towards erectile walk and run	The adaptation-evolution of spine for those higher loads has not been completed/optimal
Unhealthy postural and sedentarism at workplace	Long work hours create higher probability of early lumbar spine disorders
Yearly prevalence of back pain (LBP) is estimated to range from 15% to 20% in the US and from 25% to 45% in Europe [4-20].	Health services costs increase and new clinical and basic research is needed

Spinal Biomechanics and Spinal-Pathology Recent Advances with concise new Treatments

The lumbar spine holds the head biomechanical system and the bigger thorax-abdomen one. It can be considered a biomechanical rather complicated system. There are a number of important factors, Table 1, and for example,

1. Vertebra loads are high but changing. The vertebra-load is about 500 N during most lifetime in normal posture, [1-3 mainly] . However, when any patient lifts a weight, the reaction forces over the lumbar disk could reach around 6.000 N [3]. The reason is that there is a rather high force produced

by erector spinae [3], and the bending moment also has an important biomechanical role.

2. The spine and lumbar and cervical spine biowear along average lifetime has caused by recent changes in life lifestyles. Therefore, loads and constant forced movemennts are more frequent and higher than other biomechanical systems. This implies that osteo-pathological lesions get a high probability to occur.

The biomechanical system shows a rather complicated number of particular characteristics. This absence of links among symptoms and objective lesions, can be found almost frequently in clinical practice, both in young, mature, or older patients, namely, osteophites, spine deviations, scoliosis, and teenager spine deviations are radiologically-diagnosed in routinary health checks but the patient has not talked any subjective symptoms [18]. In this sense, it is found just the opposite, patients with movement difficulties, painful symptoms and indicators, for example paresthasias, or sciatica ones, do not show in radiological or CT/MRI explorations objective lesion confirmations—or sometimes are so insignificant that can become unnoticed at imaging data. For instance, because of radiological-density, in CT/MRI images, nerve tissue is more difficult for diagnosis than pathological osteo-signs.

Therefore, in an improvement-review from previous publications, Author’s Proposal at Biomechanical Figures 1-2, in shown. The basic spine functional unit is formed by two subsequent vertebrae united by the intervertebral disk, not as classically was considered by way of vertebrae and disks independently. This spinal-biomechanical model, Appendix [16, Casesnoves-Bioengineering-Laboratory-Specimen-Model-4] is formed by two similar-parallelepipedic masses (vertebrae) united by springs and a damper, better an hydraulic damper at center. It constitutes a very simple model with several degrees of freedom, Biomechanical Figures 1-2, and Appendix. At Biomechanical Figure 2, the Lagrangian coordinate systems are set. Therefore, the basic functional spine as a whole can be biomechanically compared to the miosine and actine overlapping in the muscle fibers. The spine biodynamics can be considered as a whole biomechanical-functional unit constituted by the linkage of these subunits. The spine biomechanical system, was created and optimized by nature along millions of years, and its biokinematics has a rather complicated biomechanical forces, biostatic, and biodynamics-movements. This remarkable biomechanical system made by nature for humans and a large number of species, even fish, its functional task for long time survival in animals/humans deals with a rather number of pathological problems during the lifetime. All the thorax-load and head-neck systems need be stabilized and supported by spine and hip. Down to the hip, there is second also complicated biomechanical system whose more susceptible parts to suffer traumatological problems are the hip and knees, and have to support and balance that first biomechanical system load

during the walk and run mainly. Specially the knees show in high percentage of young patients traumatological difficulties because at knees, the concentration of forces combined with a large variety of movements cause a high probability of injuries. For this number and other reasons, the spine prevalence/incidence of stability diseases, such as traumatic injuries, deviations, scoliosis, kyphosis, spondylolisthesis, disk hernias and other disk pathologies, among others which are not insignificant or the least ones. All these biomechanical/traumatological causes led/ forced both the surgical specialization and surgery prosthesis, instrumentation and orthopaedics industry to develop a large variety of medical-mechanical systems, super-specialized instrumentation, surgical-theatre techniques during centuries and surgical-robotics recently. In terms of biomechanics and mathematical biomodels, one important spinal geometrical 3D location is the Instantaneous Rotation Center of the disk and vertebrae, that has a significant consequence for bending moment calculations and other important biodynamics parameters, or design of artificial disks and prostheses [21].

Table 2.- Brief of Incidence and Prevalence of Lumbar Osteoarthritis and specially arthrosis lesions [24-35, 36] with complementary explanations. Remark: all database from other authors is set as references numbers.

STATISTICAL-EPIDEMIOLOGICAL CAUSES OF LBP CORRESPONDING TO SEGMENT L4-L5 [Author's proposal based on [3,10,11]]
L4-L5 supports all trunk biomechanical load, therefore, the probability of disk herniation and vertebral disorders is higher. Loads at lumbar segments are around 500 N, and could create substantial deflection of the endplate (up to 0.5 mm) [this numerical data from 3 , page 47].
L4-L5 segment forms an important part for the spine-hip union, therefore, additional biomechanical forces during all any movement dynamics are added. Not only flexion-extension, but also trunk rotations, lateral flexion-extension movements, etc,
Being the union between trunk and inferior walk biodynamics system, the Newton reactions forces during walk and running, standing up, or legs enforced movements, create an additional pressure over L4-L5 segment and its intervertebral disk,
Spine musculoskeletal system is not an insolated part of the body biomechanics. Its interaction with trunk muscles, such as erector spinae and spinal ligaments creates a rather complicated biodynamics system that implies difficulty to obtain both precise biomechanical models, calculations and simulations. Bending moments when lifting weights or normal flexion-extension movements also are significant factors.
The human evolution for standing-walking up has created additional and different loads on the L4-L5 segment and overall spine. As it is proven, the human posture has changed during human evolution, a significant difference from primates [35] .

At Table 2, the more epidemiological and statistical frequent causes of LBP correspond to lumbar spine segment L4-L5. This is confirmed by series of publications in literature with both *in vivo* imaging (MRI, CT, RX, etc) and *in vitro* necropsia database, for example [3,10,11]. Authors's specific and guessed criterion about biomedical/biomechanical

reasons for this clinical and experimental L4-L5 pathological evidence is shown Table 2.

Along the history of Medicine, lumbar spine traumatological and neurological pathology is extensive, frequent, and varied [refs 1,8 mainly] . Figure 1 shows how osteophytes-osteoarthritis can be detected also in routinary RX-explorations, [2, Casesnoves-Bioengineering-Laboratory-Specimen-311]. The objectives of this study are to develop from previous parts, and explain/detail how CAD digital necropsy, based on cloud data scanning methods, with new/different lumbar cadaveric specimens can be useful to extract reumathological signs, initial diagnosis, pathological evidences and epidemiological statistics. This following study, is focused on computational systems CAD comparisons, epidemiological incidence/prevalence of osteoarthritis, disk degeneration, vertebral plates deformations, and lumbar spine curvature distortions. The emphasis is set on cloud-data scanning CAD and imaging-processing methods, now with GNU-Octave and Matlab, with clear explanations and distinct details, illustrated along a series of CAD images and camera graphics software-engineered with Matlab . Images are designed to provide with a fast/precise perception of digital specimens, and make available emerging concepts for applications-extrapolations at other medical/surgical branches/specializations.

In this study and the literature, both with Matlab and GNU-Octave, Surfactual Computer Aided Design (CAD) and Computer Aided Manufacturing (CAM) methods have been integrated to modern biomedical research methods. Here, the epidemiological-statistical study of vertebral shape, facets, ligaments, curvature, 3D-geometry at necropsia and during different stages of any disease or normal lifetime can supply imaging database for surgical pre-post-operative planning or instrumentation manufacturing. Remark, however, that cadaveric specimens belong to rather older patients. Besides, it is useful, as an objective of this continuing study, for evaluation of incidence/prevalence of spinal disorders. CAD and CAM are widely used for industrial design of orthopaedics prostheses/apparatus [25,26]. Namely, orthopaedics prostheses, spinal instrumentation, spinal screws, stabilization kits, artificial intervertebral disks, grips, stabilization frames, etc.

Figure 1.-From previous study, [2, Casesnoves-Bioengineering-Laboratory-Specimen-3.11]. Illustrative-

example of a routinary RX thorax PA example that shows how early osteophytes of age-degeneration osteoarthritis can be detected during simple radiological explorations. At thoracic spine, two osteophytes are clear (red circles) and thoracic spine alignment is slightly deviated (green arrow). Patient: male of 65 years old without any pathology. The image of osteophytes corresponds to a diffusive peak or elongation along the borders of vertebral plates. Cardiac and pulmonary images do not show any alteration, and there are not signs of osteoporosis, bronchial ramifications and vascularity is also normal. As said, there are not a sharp link between LBP or spine pain and RX findings. This ageing-normal alteration does not implies a significant pathology unless its size and surrounding structures/nerves are not pressed or damaged. This our laboratory specimen signs are also detailed by other authors, for example [15]. [Casesnoves Bioengineering Laboratory Software 19.26].

Table 3.- From previous publications review, explanations and precision about Aged-related disorders are related to Incidence and Prevalence of Lumbar Osteoarthritis and specially arthrosis lesions [24-36] with complementary justifications. Remark: all database from other authors is set as references numbers.

AGED-RELATED LUMBAR SPINE DEGENERATION DIAGNOSIS [1-15, 20, 25-31,33]	
CAUSES	CLINICAL-BIOMECHANICAL CONSEQUENCES AND COMPLEMENTARY
Human beings stand up evolution and erect walking. Weights lifting in daily life and physical work or sports	Lumbar spine degenerates before than other musculoskeletal tissues/body biomechanical systems Sedentarism and accumulation of sit down daily work hours cause higher lumbar spine loads.
Genetic Factors	It depends on priors in ancestors medical low back pain history. Some persons genetically get a tendency for faster lumbar degeneration in osteo-biomechanical system.
Intervertebral disk physiological nutrition (proteoglicans mainly, elastic fibers, condrocites)	Both nucleous pulposus and cartilage do not have vascularization. Could be seen as a failure in fast Darwinist evolution/adaptation. Remind the elastic fibers never regenerates, the opposite of collagen fibers.
Osteoporosis	Specially in women and low physical exercise consequences. Diet and concomitant disease influences.
Surrounding ligaments and muscles degeneration of fibers misalignment.	Faster lumbar spine alteration/disorders probability. Postural, physical work, sedentarism.

Introduction of the Mathematical-Biomechanical Model of Spine Sub-Units with initial Lagrange Equations [16,

Casesnoves-Bioengineering-Laboratory-Specimen-Model-4].

This subsection show biomechanical and mathematical details of the Sub-Units Spine Model and a basic sketch, Figures 2-3.. The main equations to be applied for Lagrangian analysis are,

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{F}_1 &= K_1 \cdot \vec{x}_1 \text{ for elastic law, } \vec{x}_1 : \text{vector position ;} \\ \vec{F}_2 &= K_2 \cdot \vec{x}_2 \text{ for dumper ; } \vec{x}_2 : \text{vector velocity ;} \end{aligned}$$

where,

F₁ (Vector) : Hook's Law force .

K₁ (Scalar) : Hook's Law spring constant .

X₁ (Vector) : Spring elongation .

F₂ (Vector) : Dumper force.

K₂ (Scalar) : Dumper constant.

X₂ (Vector velocity) : Dumper velocity displacement.

(1)

Biomechanical Figure 1.- [16, Casesnoves-Bioengineering-Laboratory-Specimen-Model-4].

Simplification of Biomechanical-Concept of the lumbar vertebral-functional unit Casesnoves Model. It is formed by two masses (vertebras) united by springs and a damper at center, better an hydraulic damper, which is a very simplified model sketch with several degrees of freedom. The extremes of damper have a semi-spherical mechanical-articulation that can rotate around xyz axes. Damper corresponds to nucleus pulposus modelling, and the springs simulate the elastic fiber tissue of fibrous annulus. Springs could also simulate the most important ligaments, namely Anterior Longitudinal ligament, Posterior Longitudinal and Ligament Flavum. Equations

system and Lagrangian has been developed by Author at Bioengineering Laboratory. [Casesnoves Bioengineering Laboratory Software 19.27].

Biomechanical Figure 2.- [16, Casesnoves-Bioengineering-Laboratory-Specimen-Model-4]. Lagrangian coordinates axes simplification of Anterior Flexion Biomechanical-Concept of the lumbar vertebral-functional unit Casesnoves Model. It is formed by two masses (vertebras) with one coordinates system each one. They are united by springs and a damper at center, better an hydraulic damper with its proper dynamical constants, which is a very shortened model sketch with several degrees of freedom. Both coordinates systems get constraints equations and angles. The extremes of the damper have a semi-spherical mechanical-articulation that can rotate around xyz axes, therefore the movements are in 3D. Namely, flexion, extension, left bending or right bendind (lateral bendings/flexions), and rotations. Equations system and Lagrangian has been developed by Author at Bioengineering Laboratory. [Casesnoves Bioengineering Laboratory Software 19.28]. Enhanced in Appendix.

Table 4.- Review of Incidence and Prevalence of Lumbar Osteoarthritis and specially arthrosis lesions [24-36] with complementary explanations. Remark: all database from other authors is set as references numbers.

BRIEF OF LUMBAR OSTEOARTHRITIS-ARTHROSIS RELATED TO THIS STUDY		
LUMBAR SPINAL DISORDER	DATABASE	ADDITIONAL
Patients with a spinal disorder whose etiology is unclear [3]	= 85%	[3]
Lifetime prevalence of LBP	= 75-85%	The lifetime prevalence for irradiated leg pain seems to be about half that of back pain in general, and the lifetime prevalence of sciatic pain is estimated to be much lower, approximately 3–5% [3].
Economical Social Cost	Most of studies coincide it is in general high	Two main reasons: causes of work leave and health insurance diagnosis and treatment high cost. From [3]: Work-related disability from non-specific spinal disorders has become epidemic in industrialized countries.
From [10] Prevalence of Lumbar Spine Arthrosis	From [10]: Facet arthrosis was present in 53% (L1–L2), 66% (L2–L3), 72% (L3–L4), 79% (L4–L5), and 59% (L5–S1).	Remark: arthrosis is an exclusively degenerative disease with No ethiological causes from immunology factors (Arthritis Reumatoid), infections, or metabolic (Uric Acid). Those are other types of Osteoarthritis.
From [10] Prevalence of Lumbar Spine Arthrosis by Age	From [10] : coincidence with this cadaveric study results: facet arthrosis was present in 57% of 20- to 29-year-olds, 82% of 30- to 39-year-olds, 93% of 40- to 49-year-olds, 97% in 50- to 59-year-olds, and 100% in those older than 60 years old.	Coincidence with this cadaveric study results in age segment older than 60 years old. Table 2.
From [10]: Overall Prevalence of Facet Arthrosis	Overall prevalence of facet arthrosis, age-independent. For Age-dependent the results is the same.	This data matches in general other author's studies [3-15].
Prevalence of Face joint Arthrosis, from [8]	Male 20% Female 80%	Lumbar spinal stenosis(LSS) and facet joint arthrosis (FJA) are important causes for low back pain.
Anatomical Lumbar Region Prevalence of facet joint arthrosis	From [8] : The prevalence of FJA increases cranial-caudally from L1 to L5, and the highest incidence being at the L4-L5 spinal level.	It is most important than FJA the arthrosis localized at vertebral bodies, facets and plates.

Objectives of the Research

Therefore, the study main objectives are several: firstly present sharply the 3D CAD method to get clearer and more uncovering imaging-processing from lumbar vertebra cadaveric specimens. This image-processing implementation is done with Matlab and GNU-Octave, comparing both. Secondly, obtain/make epidemiological statistical records, up-to-date, for orthopedics-biomechanics clinical, diagnosis, research, biomechanical database, and biomedical industrial spinal-manufacturing applications. The presentation improvements of the sub-unit spine biomechanical model from [16, Casesnoves-Bioengineering-Laboratory-Specimen-Model-4], Figures 2-3 are included with dynamic-axes outlined.

In brief, a forward advance 3D imaging processing with two systems for a new cadaveric lumbar spine is shown. That specimen is anatomically, statistically and epidemiologically diagnosed. The second stage of the spine mathematical sub-units model is represented and biomechanically detailed [16, Casesnoves-Bioengineering-Laboratory-Specimen-Model-4].

II. COMPUTATIONAL METHODS AND CAD REUMATHOLOGICAL DIAGNOSIS

In Flux-Diagram 1, the structure of the engineered software is displayed/simplified. The systems used are GNU-Octave and Matlab (2024). The image processing in GNU-Octave takes an average of 2-4 seconds longer. One of the most important characteristics for the program is related to the programmer experience in both systems. That is, to obtain an optimal 3D image requires skills and preparation in CAD with anatomic-cadaveric specimens. Just observe that there are many variants in the patterns that could be set, it was tried to implement the minimum-run-time one.

Flux-Diagram 1.- Basic programming method steps for getting 3D image processing with Matlab. GNU-Octave is simpler and has less tools. Note that the experience of the programmer to obtain a good image-processing is essential.

This section is based on 3D image processing improvements from previous publications and diagnosis/exploration with clinical evaluation of pathological signs found in the specimen. It is developed in a 3D image-series steps with explanations and details about the imaging-processing tools that were implemented and their respective importance. Any individual and particular reumathological sign is marked properly [8, 9, 10, 15] .

CAD Step 1.-Upper Matlab, lower GNU-Octave. The cadaveric specimen general first view. Medial to lateral direction, cranial to caudal, and posterior to anterior are set. The image processing color is set simple in first overview. Vertebral bodies, disks, plates, and osteoarthritis signs. After that, it will be necessary to rotate the specimen searching the best vision angles and projections. The size of the image can be changed proportionally. [Casesnoves Bioengineering Laboratory Software 19.28]

CAD Step 2.-Upper Matlab, lower GNU-Octave. Pursuing a sharper/detailed image, the camera image-processing was applied. L2-4 anterior vertebral surfaces are relatively clear. It is necessary to adjust the image color and Delaunay tiles magnitude. The first diagnosis, for instance, for L2 can begin be guessed, there is an anterior clear osteoarthritis deformation at anterior-central vertebral facet . [Casesnoves Bioengineering Laboratory Software 19.30]

CAD Step 3.-Matlab camera findings at L5 anterior plate degeneration deformities. The same process has to be followed for all specimen vertebrae and disks. Note that between both main findings the anterior border shows also degeneration signs. There are significant deformities at L4-L5 disk. It is necessary to rotate, select contrast through color choice and carefully examine the different perspectives to reveal sharply the pathological findings. [Casesnoves Bioengineering Laboratory Software 19.31]

CAD Step 4.-GNU-Octave L5 caudal and border plates. Very sharp image for L5 and L4-L5 disk. The anterior herniations of the L5-S1 can create pressure of nerve roots with acute pain and paresthesias. The herniations could also correspond to effects of cadaveric specimen experimental work. In this specimens it is not possible to view the facet joints. The image is a bit forced but shows well right side of L5. It is easy to detect vertebral body degeneration. [Casesnoves Bioengineering Laboratory Software 19.32]

CAD Step 4.1.-GNU-Octave L5 caudal and border plates. Very sharp image for L5 and L4-L5 disk. The anterior herniations of the L5-S1 can create pressure of nerve roots with acute pain and paresthesias. The herniations could also correspond to effects of cadaveric specimen experimental work. In this specimens it is not possible to view the facet joints. [Casesnoves Bioengineering Laboratory Software 19.33]

CAD Step 4.2.-Matlab Caudal and cranial border plates main deformities in L4 are marked and detected. The anterior herniations of the L5-S1 and L4-L5 disks could be anterior herniations, which are not frequent since usually the disk herniation is posterior and creates pressure of nerve roots with acute pain and paresthesias. The herniations could also correspond to effects of cadaveric specimen experimental

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work. In this specimens it is not possible to view the facet joints. [Casesnoves Bioengineering Laboratory Software 19.34] .

CAD Step 5.-Matlab camera tilt and rotation to get imaging-process of cranial specimen zone. Severe lesions at L3 vertebral body and plate borders. Deformities at right lateral part. A probable osteophyte detected for at the left lateral part of L4 vertebra. L2 vertebral body is well conserved. The general conservation of this specimen is acceptable. [Casesnoves Bioengineering Laboratory Software 19.35]

CAD Step 6.- Matlab camera orbit-scene imaging highlighting process and tilt with rotation to get imaging-process of cranial specimen zone. Severe lesions at L3 vertebral body and plate borders. Deformities at right lateral part. L2 vertebral body is well conserved, but with orbit-scene a L2 cranial anterior deformity is diagnosed. [Casesnoves Bioengineering Laboratory Software 19.36]

III. EXTENSION AND REVIEW OF CLINICAL REUMATHOLOGICAL RESULTS

The results of CAD analysis of specimen are detailed in Table 5. All vertebrae and disks show reumathological alteration signs. The most frequent ones found is arthrosis and deformation of vertebral plates. Since specimen is cadaveric, the age-related changes are sharply evident. However, in previous publications, the vertebral anterior surface regions of

interest (ROIs) were mathematically modeled with an hyperboloid equation and optimized with Inverse Least Squares methods [25,26] .

Table 5.-Reumathological-Diagnosis. The findings coincide with previous publications [3,8,10,11].

BRIEF OF LUMBAR CLINICAL REUMATHOLOGICAL APPLICATIONS	
SPINAL SURGICAL PATHOLOGY FIELD	APPLICATIONS DATABASE AND ADDITIONAL
Lumbar Spinal CAD	All tools and prostheses optimal design
Lumbar Spinal CAM	All tools and prostheses optimal manufacturing design
Spine tools and surgical apparatus and prostheses	Spinal instrumentation, implants and deformity correction prostheses, implant-bone optimal interfaces instrumentation, all kind of screws, rods, grips, distractors, screw-insertion-angle optimization for a wide range of implants
Design of Precise Prostheses	All types of implants, artificial disks, clamps, stabilizers, etc
Orthopedics Applications	Spondylolisthesis, scoliosis, and all other types of deformations orthopedics apparatus
Pre-operation Failure Probability Prediction and Control	Pre-operation computational simulations/optimization, pre-operation design of implants or necessary new tools at theatre
Post-operation Failure Probability Prediction and Control	Complications prevention, post-operation tracking, imaging post-operation computational checking, design of necessary additional post-operation implants
Functional and Post Surgery Rehabilitation	Post-surgery orthopaedics rehabilitation for motion

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The objectives of the study were the confirmation of necropsia-diagnosis of reumathological signs in lumbar cadaveric specimens with CAD computational methods by using in this Part III GNU Octave contrasted with Matlab. Special aim was checking both systems capabilities, advantages, inconvenients, and observe what is the best choice when using them alternatively.

The second aim was to compare and obtain verification of RX, MRI and CT database pathological data published in literature [8,9]. Additional research was to show the Lagrange fundamental equations biomechanical base for the vertebral unit model developed recently, [16, Casesnoves-Bioengineering-Laboratory-Specimen-Model-4], Figures 2-3.

Furthermore, the included LBP and reumathological research-review shows statistical, epidemiological, and incidence-prevalence data given by some recent publications [3-18], Tables 1-2. It was explained at introduction, modern computational applications on current lumbar spine diagnosis, age-related lumbar degeneration, biodynamics applications, and future investigation lines.

GNU Octave and Matlab 3D imaging processing methods for resolution in improved vertebral contrast/facets/positioning, angle-rotation, vertebral-anatomical parts separation, visualization of overall and parts of lumbar spines, and different 3D imaging options available, are explained and demonstrated. For clinical medical physics and computational anatomical pathology, these innovations to

improve previous imaging contributions and statistical data are demonstrated.

The 3D CAD Imaging-processing results show sharpness and acceptable clarity of anterior lumbar vertebrae images. The improvements of this study have been the better use of camera vision and optimization of rotations, tilt, perspectives, and contrasts to get sharp verified diagnosis. Statistical results section, Table 2, show the reumathological diagnosis particularly oriented for lumbar arthrosis.

A significant objective first inconvenience of this method is that to get clear and precise images takes time. There are many 3D Imaging-processing tools to be selected to obtain the optimal picture. The software-programmer experience plays an important role in this task.

The second difficulty/relative obstacle is numerical. The matrices of the software have to be carefully prepared to get the maximum clarity/definition for 3D imaging processing. The tiles of Delanuy triangulation method size constitute an important part in this task.

Supplementary, and a suggestion, is that the lumbar cadaveric specimens should be cut better, anatomical-pathological better prepared, and finer scanned at their complete anatomy for enhanced studies. The cloud point data could be increased in data number and precision significance to improve the CAD 3D Imaging quality.

In brief, following this article series, with new lumbar cadaveric specimen, and based on previous software GNU and Matlab advances, this Part III shows a complementary for reumathological arthrosis with orthopedics applications. Computational 3D imaging-processing methods with both systems were explained/detailed step by step. Results prove epidemiological-statistical dataset for L2–L5 in cadaveric-specimens necropsia with resume of clinical and industrial applications in reumathology. The functional sub-unit biomechanical spine model was shown with further Lagrangian and biomechanical equations.

V. SCIENTIFIC ETHICS STANDARDS

New important remarks: (1) important : software, text, images, whole article is made by author, and no artificial intelligence programs, systems, or software for making the paper was used, according to standard european union and scientific community ethics. if AI were used at any of the publications, it is precisely said what was used, how and the article parts. (2) images and table-data reminders from previous contributions are intended for explicit improved understanding . Additional Statistical Data are from authors at [2-18] . Model [16, Casesnoves-Bioengineering-Laboratory-Specimen-Model-4], Figure 2, belongs to Casesnoves Intellectual property and Casesnoves Bioengineering Laboratory. Figure 1 RX image belongs to Casesnoves Bioengineering Laboratory, [2, Casesnoves-Bioengineering-Laboratory-Specimen-3.11].This contribution is based on Graphical Visualization-

Optimization methods for different clinical laboratory cadaveric specimens of lumbar spine, namely Specimen 10. 3D Imaging Computational Methods were created by Francisco Casesnoves from 2007-2019. Forensic Robotics Integrated Systems engineering-concepts were developed by Casesnoves in July 2020. This study was carried out, and their contents are done according to the European Union Technology and Science Ethics. Reference, ‘European Textbook on Ethics in Research’. European Commission, Directorate-General for Research. Unit L3. Governance and Ethics. European Research Area. Science and Society. EUR 24452 EN [38,39]. This research was completely done by the author, the software, calculations, images, mathematical propositions and statements, reference citations, and text is original for the authors. When anything is taken from a source, it is adequately recognized. Ideas from previous publications were emphasized due to a clarification aim, [38,39]. When a citation such as [Casesnoves, ‘year’] is set, it is exclusively to clarify intellectual property at current times, without intention to brag. The article is exclusively scientific, without any commercial, institutional, academic, any religious, religious-similar, non-scientific theories, personal opinions, political ideas, or economical influences. When anything is taken from a source, it is adequately recognized. Ideas and some text expressions/sentences from previous publications were emphasized due to a clarification aim. Number of references is large to provide literature in open access for public health care institutions.

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APPENDIX

$$\vec{F}_1 = K_1 \cdot \vec{x}_1 \text{ for elastic law , } \vec{x}_1 : \text{vector position ;}$$

$$\vec{F}_2 = K_2 \cdot \vec{x}_2 \text{ for dumper ; } \vec{x}_2 : \text{vector velocity ;}$$

where,

F_1 (Vector) : Hook's Law force .

K_1 (Scalar) : Hook's Law spring constant .

X_1 (Vector) : Spring elongation .

F_2 (Vector) : Dumper force.

K_2 (Scalar) : Dumper constant.

X_2 (Vector velocity) : Dumper velocity displacement.

Biomechanical Figure 2.- Appendix-Enhanced, and Lagrange initial Equations. [16, Casesnoves-Bioengineering-Laboratory-Specimen-Model-4]. Biomechanical model first steps to set coordinates system to obtain the Lagrange equations and mathematical development. Lagrangian coordinates axes simplification of Anterior Flexion Biomechanical-Concept of the lumbar vertebral-functional unit Casesnoves Model. It is formed by two masses (vertebras) with one coordinates system each one. They are united by springs and a damper at center, better an hydraulic damper with its proper dynamical constants, which is a very shortened model sketch with several degrees of freedom. Both coordinates systems get constraints equations and angles. The extremes of the damper have a semi-spherical mechanical-articulation that can rotate around xyz axes, therefore the movements are in 3D. Namely, flexion, extension, left bending or right bendind (lateral bendings/flexions), and rotations. Equations system and Lagrangian has been developed by Author at Bioengineering Laboratory. [Casesnoves Bioengineering Laboratory Software 19.28].